

Hyper-volatile Entrapment in Interstellar Ice Analogues

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ABSTRACT

Planets and planetesimals acquire their volatile reservoir through ice and gas accretion in protoplanetary disks. The distribution of volatiles between solid and gas phases within these disks thus determines the quantity of volatiles accreted onto a solid core or gaseous atmosphere of planets forming throughout different disk regions. The entrapment of hyper-volatiles in less volatile ices allows the hyper-volatile to remain solid beyond its sublimation temperature, producing more complex chemical profiles than what would be expected for simple snowline models. This study uses laboratory experiments to explore the ability of several abundant interstellar ices (H₂O, CO₂, NH₃, CH₃OH, and C₂H₆) to trap key hyper-volatile components, (CO, CH₄, N₂, and Ar). The entrapment efficiencies of these ices are measured for each hyper-volatile through temperature programmed desorption (TPD) experiments. During the TPD, the ice is heated at a rate of 1 K/min, and the desorption of both the hyper-volatile and ice species is detected using a quadrupole mass spectrometer (QMS) and further monitored by infrared (IR) spectroscopy.

Preliminary results find entrapment efficiencies around 60% for H₂O and CO₂, aligning with fiducial efficiencies previously reported. Entrapment in NH₃ ices showed comparable efficiencies to H₂O and CO₂, suggesting an entrapment mechanism that operates independently of the chemical properties of both the hyper-volatile and ice species. However, the entrapment efficiencies for CH₃OH and C₂H₆ diverged drastically from this trend; less than 10% entrapment was observed for mixtures of N₂ and Ar in CH₃OH; the observed entrapment efficiencies for mixtures of CO, CH₄, N₂, and Ar in C₂H₆ were 30%, 10%, 70%, and 40% respectively. To further investigate the peculiar entrapment patterns observed for CH₃OH and C₂H₆ matrices, entrapment efficiencies were re-calculated using a new method – defined for this study as β -entrapment – that includes hyper-volatile desorption occurring at temperatures between the sublimation temperatures of the hyper-volatile and ice matrix. Using the β -entrapment definition (as opposed to the previously used α -entrapment definition that only includes co-desorbing hyper-volatiles) to calculate entrapment efficiency did produce results more comparable for all hyper-volatiles across all matrix species. Nevertheless, further investigation into the entrapment mechanism, particularly for organic matrix species, is likely warranted to completely understand entrapment as a whole. A complete understanding of entrapment and a comprehensive catalogue of entrapment efficiencies would provide the framework to explain and predict the volatile ratios in protoplanetary disks and their subsequent planets.

1. INTRODUCTION

Planets and planetesimals form around new stars from the accretion of gas, dust, and ice in protoplanetary disks (Raymond & Morbidelli 2022; Simon 2023). These protoplanetary disks, composed of matter gravitationally bound to and rotating around a newly formed star, contain the chemical reservoir for the planets that will eventually form in them. As such, the chemical composition of planets can be estimated by the chemical make-up of the protoplanetary disk in the region where the planet forms (Oberg & Bergin 2020; Simon 2023).

Volatiles, defined in astrochemistry as atomic or molecular species of relatively low sublimation temperatures (below a few hundred Kelvin), account for most of the condensable matter in protoplanetary disks (Oberg & Bergin 2020). The distribution of volatiles between the solid and gas phases in a given region of protoplanetary disks critically affects the volatile composition of the planets that form there. In protoplanetary disks, snowlines are defined as the radial location in the disk where a given volatile “freezes out” (changes from the gas to solid phase) (Boogert 2015; Simon

2019). Since the temperature in protoplanetary disks increases towards the center star, snowline locations generally correspond to the location of a given volatile’s sublimation temperature.

Evidently, the distribution of volatiles between solids and gas is more complex than what the snowline model would suggest. Rather, very volatile species (called hyper-volatiles) such as CO, CH₄, N₂, and Argon can become entrapped in less volatile ices and thus exist as solid in protoplanetary disks closer to the star than their sublimation temperature should allow (Bar-nun 1985; Simon 2019). Entrapment describes the process by which a hyper-volatile becomes trapped in a less volatile ice matrix and is thereby able to remain solid beyond its sublimation temperature. Entrapment occurs in protoplanetary disks when the hyper-volatile and volatile are co-deposited onto an icy grain and simultaneously form an icy mantle that is a mixture of both molecular species (Simon 2023). In these ice mixtures, only a portion of the hyper-volatile is actually entrapped and thus remains solid until co-desorbing with the ice matrix. The remaining non-entrapped hyper-volatile component desorbs at its normal sublimation temperature. This process is illustrated for a mixture of the hyper-volatile CO in an H₂O ice matrix in Fig.1. The relative ability, measured in terms of entrapment efficiency, of abundant interstellar ices to entrap hyper-volatiles determines the distribution of hyper-volatiles between the solid and gas phase throughout protoplanetary disks.

Figure 1. An illustration of the process of heating up an ice mixture of CO and H₂O. As the temperature increases to 35K (the approximate sublimation temperature of CO) non-entrapped CO desorbs. The remaining entrapped CO remains solid in the ice until it co-desorbs with the H₂O at water’s sublimation temperature around 150K.

Studies have experimentally demonstrated that water (H₂O) ice is quite good at entrapping the most abundant hyper-volatile in protoplanetary disks – CO (Bar-nun 1985; Simon 2019). The ability of H₂O and CO₂ ices to entrap CO and other hyper-volatiles (CH₄, N₂, and Ar) has also been documented in Simon 2023. Interestingly, studies show comparable entrapment efficiencies for both H₂O and CO₂ ices across all hyper-volatiles for low temperature depositions. Such a result is indicative of an entrapment mechanism that operates independently of ice matrix-hyper-volatile interactions. However, further investigation into the entrapment mechanism is required in order to confirm this hypothesis. Specifically, the entrapment of hyper-volatiles in more ice matrices should be investigated to uncover whether this species independent entrapment mechanism is observed for additional ices. Furthermore, protoplanetary disks contain ices other than water and CO₂. As such, the entrapment efficiencies for these ices ought to be determined in order to provide a more accurate astrochemical portfolio of protoplanetary disks and their subsequent planetary components.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1. *Experimental set-up*

The experimental set-up used in these experiments is designed to investigate thermal processes in interstellar ice analogs and is described in detail in Simon 2023. In brief, the central unit consists of a 6.5” ultra-high vacuum (UHV) chamber, which reaches a base pressure of approximately 4×10^{-9} torr at room temperature. The UHV chamber is situated in the sample compartment of a Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrometer with a liquid N₂ cooled Mercury Cadmium Telluride detector. The FTIR is housed on a separate, vibrationally isolated frame, such that the IR optical path is horizontally aligned with the chamber. A quadrupole mass spectrometer (QMS) connected to the chamber is used to monitor the composition of gas in the chamber. Mounted on an optical ring sample holder connected to a closed cycle helium cryostat, an IR-transparent 2mm thick CsI substrate window is suspended at the center of the UHV chamber. A differentially pumped rotary seal attached to the sample holder allows for full 360

deg rotation within the chamber. Reaching a base temperature of 12K, the CsI substrate is kept cold, allowing for gas phase mixtures to condense into ice when encountering the substrate. These gaseous mixtures are mixed prior to deposition in a stainless-steel gas-line attached to the chamber via a 4.8 mm diameter tube doser.

2.2. Experimental Procedure

Aiming to investigate the effect of different ice matrices on the entrapment of various hyper-volatiles, this study chooses to investigate the entrapment of four hyper-volatiles (^{13}CO , CH_4 , $^{15}\text{N}_2$, and Ar) in five ice matrices (H_2O , CO_2 , NH_3 , CH_3OH , and C_2H_6). Both the hyper-volatile and ice species were chosen based on their relative abundance in protoplanetary disks (Oberg & Bergin 2020). The experimental series tests individual mixtures of each hyper-volatile in each ice matrix with ice to hyper-volatile ratios of 10:1, and an overall ice thickness of 50ML. This results in a total of 20 unique mixtures.

Each mixture is prepared in the gas-line around 30 minutes prior to the experiment. The matrix species and hyper-volatile are added individually, and the relative amounts of each are monitored using the pressure gauges in the line. Once mixed, the gas is dosed into the chamber at a temperature of 10K and deposited as an ice onto the sample holder which is positioned to be perpendicular to the gas stream. The ice thickness is continually measured using FTIR, and the dose is stopped once the desired ice thickness is achieved. During the dose, infrared spectra are continuously generated from the average of 32 scans, each with a 1 cm^{-1} resolution measuring frequencies from 800 cm^{-1} to 4000 cm^{-1} . Background spectra are taken prior to the dose once the chamber has cooled to 10K. Generated from the average of 64 scans, the backgrounds are subtracted from the spectra recorded during the dose. The ice thickness can be calculated from the following equation:

$$N_i = \frac{\cos \theta \int \tau_i(v) dv}{A_i} \quad (1)$$

Here, N_i gives the column density (molecule cm^{-2}); θ is the angle of incidence between the IR field vector and the ice surface normal; the integral $\int \tau_i(v) dv$ corresponds to the integrated optical depth of a chosen IR band; and A_i is the characteristic band strength of the molecular species. In the experimental setup, θ is 45 degrees when the sample holder is perpendicular to the doser (as is the case during the dose), and 0 degrees when the sample holder is perpendicular to the IR optical path. The column density is converted to monolayers (ML) by applying the conversion factor of 10^{15} molecules cm^{-2} . For the IR active hyper-volatiles (^{13}CO and CH_4), this equation is also used to determine the precise mixing ratio achieved in each mixture.

Once the dosing is complete, the ice mixture undergoes a temperature programmed desorption (TPD), during which the ice is heated at a ramp rate 1 K/min until both components of the ice completely desorb. The desorption of both the hyper-volatile and ice species is detected using the QMS and summarized in corresponding TPD curves. Additionally, regular IR spectra are taken throughout the TPD (64 scans each, corresponding to approximately 1 spectra every 1.5 minutes) and these can be used to assess the structure and composition of the ice throughout the TPD.

Fig.2 gives an example of a TPD curve for a ^{13}CO and H_2O mixture. The TPD curve plots the QMS signal for a given m/z value over temperature. Since the QMS only detects molecules in the gas phase, the area under the TPD curve is proportional to the number of molecules of the given m/z desorbed over a finite temperature range. If distinct, non-overlapping m/z values are chosen for the hyper-volatile and ice species, the desorption of the two components can be distinguished. In all TPD curves generated from the experiments in this study, the TPD curves for the ice matrix species have only one peak that occurs at the end of the TPD and corresponds to the characteristic sublimation temperature of the ice species. On the other hand, the hyper-volatile TPD curves often have multiple peaks, including a peak around the hyper-volatile's signature sublimation temperature corresponding to non-entrapped hyper-volatile desorbing, and a peak around the sublimation temperature of the ice matrix that illustrates the co-desorption of entrapped hyper-volatile with the ice matrix. In addition to these two characteristic hyper-volatile peaks, intermediate peaks were also observed for several mixtures. The scientific explanation for these peaks and the contribution towards the entrapment efficiency will be explored more in the discussion.

The entrapment efficiency for a given mixture is calculated by taking the integrated area under the hyper-volatile curve, and dividing the proportion of the hyper-volatile considered to be 'entrapped' by the total.

3. RESULTS

Figure 2. An example TPD plot. This plot corresponds to the mixture of ^{13}CO in H_2O ice. The blue line, corresponding to $m/z = 18$, represents H_2O . The orange line, corresponding to $m/z = 29$, represents ^{13}CO .

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3.1. Defining Entrapment

In the experiments and analysis conducted in Simon (2019) and (2023), entrapment is considered to only include the proportion of the hyper-volatile that remains trapped for the duration of the TPD, desorbing only with the ice matrix in a final co-desorption event. As such, entrapment efficiency is calculated for a given mixture by dividing the integrated area under the hyper-volatile's co-desorption peak by the total area under the hyper-volatile curve. We will denote this co-desorption method of calculating entrapment as the α -entrapment efficiency.

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While this definition of entrapment was suitable for the H_2O and CO_2 ice mixtures in Simon (2019) and (2023), the diversity of matrix species in this study produces more complex hyper-volatile desorption patterns that demand we consider another definition of entrapment. For the CO_2 , NH_3 , CH_3OH , and C_2H_6 ices, hyper-volatile desorption is observed at intermediate temperatures between the hyper-volatile's sublimation temperature and the matrix species' sublimation temperature. IR spectra taken during the TPDs suggest that these intermediate releases of previously trapped hyper-volatile are the result of solid phase changes occurring in the ice matrix (this hypothesis will be examined further in the discussion). For CH_3OH and C_2H_6 ices in particular, the hyper-volatile desorption at these intermediate temperatures accounts for a significant proportion of the total hyper-volatile component of the ice mixtures and should thus be more thoroughly examined. We will thus consider β -entrapment to include the proportion of hyper-volatiles trapped in the ice beyond their sublimation temperatures; this would include both co-desorption and intermediate peaks in the calculation of entrapment efficiencies. Fig. 3 further illustrates the distinction between α and β -entrapment by highlighting the respective regions of integration for each method.

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3.2. Entrapment Characteristics of the Different Ice Matrices

The overall α and β -entrapment efficiencies are summarized in [Fig.7]. The following sections explore the individual entrapment patterns observed for each ice matrix.

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Figure 3. Choosing regions of integration for α and β -entrapment. For the ^{13}CO , H_2O mixture (left), the α -entrapment efficiency is calculated by taking the integrated area under the hyper-volatile curve (orange) within the region highlighted in red. For the ^{13}CO , NH_3 mixture (right), the β -entrapment efficiency is calculated by taking the integrated area under the hyper-volatile curve (orange) within the region highlighted in blue.

3.2.1. Entrapment in H_2O ice

For all H_2O mixtures, the hyper-volatile TPD curves exhibit the following two peaks: one occurring at the normal hyper-volatile sublimation temperature, and the other occurring near water’s sublimation temperature of around 150K [Fig.4]. The α -entrapment efficiencies for the H_2O mixtures are thus measured by dividing the integrated area under the co-desorption peak by the total integrated area under the hyper-volatile curve. This yields α -entrapment efficiencies of approximately 60% for all hyper-volatiles, aligning with the results from Simon (2023).

3.2.2. Entrapment in CO_2 ice

For CO_2 mixtures, hyper-volatile desorption peaks are observed at the hyper-volatile’s sublimation temperature and CO_2 ’s sublimation temperature at approximately 80K [Fig.5 (a)]. In the intermediate temperature range, there is continuous hyper-volatile desorption, indicated by a plateau in the TPD curve. For all hyper-volatiles, the α -entrapment efficiencies (including only the co-desorption peak) are calculated to be around 60%, aligning with the results from Simon (2023). Adding the continuous desorption observed between the peaks, the β -entrapment efficiencies are calculated to be around 70%. Although β -entrapment was not defined in Simon 2023, the study does also report similar increases in entrapment efficiencies for CO_2 ice matrices when intermediate temperature desorption is included.

3.2.3. Entrapment in NH_3 ice

The experiments with NH_3 yielded comparable results to the entrapment efficiencies measured for H_2O and CO_2 . In the NH_3 mixtures, the hyper-volatile TPD curves exhibit the following three distinct peaks: one occurring at the normal hyper-volatile sublimation temperature, one at NH_3 ’s sublimation temperature of approximately 95K, and an intermediate peak around 70K [Fig.5 (b)]. For all hyper-volatiles, the α -entrapment efficiency was around 60% and the β -entrapment efficiency was around 70%. As such, we observe entrapment efficiencies for NH_3 ices comparable to those observed for CO_2 and H_2O .

3.2.4. Entrapment in CH_3OH ice

The CH_3OH ices yielded a more complex series of results and TPD curves compared to H_2O , CO_2 , and NH_3 ices [Fig.6 (a)]. The TPD curves for CO , N_2 , and CH_4 in CH_3OH ices all feature the following three distinct peaks similar to those seen in NH_3 ices: one occurring at the normal hyper-volatile sublimation temperature, one at CH_3OH ’s sublimation temperature of approximately 130K, and an intermediate peak around 110K corresponding to a CH_3OH solid phase change. However, unlike NH_3 ices, the proportion of hyper-volatiles desorbing at each peak does not follow the same pattern across all hyper-volatiles. Rather, while most trapped hyper-volatiles desorb at the co-desorption

Figure 4. Hyper-volatile entrapment in H_2O ice. The region of integration used for α -entrapment is highlighted in red.

Figure 5. Hyper-volatile entrapment in (a) CO_2 and (b) NH_3 ices. The region of integration used for α -entrapment is highlighted in red. The region of integration used for β -entrapment is highlighted in blue.

peak for the CO and N_2 mixtures, the CH_4 mixture featured the highest relative desorption at the middle peak,

during the ice recrystallization. As such, while the α -entrapment efficiencies (proportional to the co-desorption peak) are approximately 60% for the CO and N₂ mixtures, the α -entrapment efficiency for the CH₄ mixture was only 10%. Interestingly, the β -entrapment efficiencies (which include the intermediate peak) calculated were more similar among CO, N₂, and CH₄ mixtures, with the β -entrapment efficiencies observed to be approximately 80% for the CO and N₂ mixtures, and approximately 60% for the CH₄ mixture.

The results for the Ar in CH₃OH mixture were the most comparably divergent. For the Ar TPD curve, no co-desorption is observed with the CH₃OH ice, yielding an α -entrapment efficiency of 0%. In CH₃OH ices, we observed all the trapped Ar desorbing at the intermediate temperature of 110K. The β -entrapment efficiency for the Ar and CH₃OH mixture is approximately 60%. As such, despite the complex hyper-volatile TPD signatures observed for CH₃OH mixtures, the overall β -entrapment efficiencies are somewhat comparable among all hyper-volatiles, and similar to β -entrapment efficiencies observed for CO₂ and NH₃ ices.

Figure 6. Hyper-volatile entrapment in (a) CH₃OH and (b) C₂H₆ ices. The region of integration used for α -entrapment is highlighted in red. The region of integration used for β -entrapment is highlighted in blue.

3.2.5. Entrapment in C₂H₆ ice

Upon first inspection, the C₂H₆ ices present different entrapment patterns for all four hyper-volatiles [Fig.6 (b)]. Nevertheless, TPD curves for all four hyper-volatiles include at least the following three peaks: one occurring at the normal hyper-volatile sublimation temperature, one at C₂H₆'s sublimation temperature of approximately 65K, and an intermediate peak around 55K. CO, N₂, and Ar mixtures appear to feature an additional initial peak before 30K, and the CH₄ mixture appears to have a peak around 35K. The identities of these peaks are uncertain. The α -entrapment efficiencies calculated were approximately 20%, 10%, 70%, and 40% for the CO, CH₄, N₂, and Ar mixtures, respectively. The β -entrapment efficiencies were calculated using the integrated area under the hyper-volatile desorption peaks located at temperatures above the hyper-volatile's sublimation temperatures (this includes the co-desorption peak and the intermediate peak at 55K, but excludes any initial peaks before the hyper-volatile's sublimation temperature). The β -entrapment efficiencies for CO, N₂, and Ar were approximately 80%, while the β -entrapment efficiency for the CH₄ mixture was approximately 50%.

3.3. Uncertainty in Entrapment Efficiency Calculations

The uncertainty of measured entrapment efficiencies is determined using dispersion-based uncertainties. Ideally, to calculate these dispersion-based uncertainties, we would run multiple experiments for each hyper-volatile and ice matrix combination. We have plans to complete this uncertainty analysis in the near future. At present, we estimate the error using the dispersion-based uncertainties meticulously calculated in Simon 2023. Since this study uses the exact same experimental set-up as used in Simon 2023, we assume that the dispersion results would be the same for

Figure 7. Summary of α and β -entrapment efficiencies.

221 overlapping hyper-volatile and ice mixtures. Simon 2023 applied a fractional uncertainty of 0.04 for all mixtures of a
 222 10:1 ice to hyper-volatile ratio. While Simon 2023 tested only H₂O and CO₂ ice matrices with all four hyper-volatiles
 223 used in this study, we will also extend the 0.04 fractional uncertainty to all NH₃, CH₃OH, and C₂H₆ ice mixtures, at
 224 least until further analysis of uncertainty is completed.

225 4. DISCUSSION

226 This study ultimately aimed to accomplish two objectives. First, the experimental series was designed to investigate
 227 the ability of five unique interstellar ices to trap four of the most abundant hyper-volatiles found in protoplanetary
 228 disks, and then explore the implications of any observed entrapment on the predicted locations of hyper-volatile
 229 snowlines. Secondly, the study also hoped to shed more light on the entrapment mechanism itself, ultimately seeking
 230 a chemical and physical understanding of observed entrapment efficiencies. Both goals will be evaluated in the first
 231 two sections of the discussion. The final section of the discussion will explore the effect of solid phase changes on
 232 hyper-volatile entrapment and the confounding evidence of these structure changes observed in IR spectral analysis.

233 4.1. Implications on protoplanetary disks and snowlines

234 All the five ice matrices featured in this study – H₂O, CO₂, NH₃, CH₃OH, and C₂H₆ – were observed to entrap all
 235 four hyper-volatiles – CO, N₂, CH₄, and Ar. By entrapment broadly, we mean to say that each of these ice matrices
 236 can cause a proportion of these hyper-volatiles to remain solid beyond their sublimation temperature. For all H₂O,
 237 CO₂, and NH₃ mixtures, as well as mixtures of CO and N₂ in CH₃OH, and N₂ in C₂H₆, most of the hyper-volatile
 238 content (approximately 60%) remains completely trapped in the solid phase until co-desorbing with the ice matrix.
 239 For the other mixtures (CH₄ and Ar in CH₃OH, and CO, CH₄, and Ar in C₂H₆), while only a small proportion of
 240 the hyper-volatiles remain solid until co-desorption, most of the hyper-volatile content still remains solid beyond the
 241 hyper-volatile sublimation temperature. The entrapment of these hyper-volatiles in H₂O, CO₂, NH₃, CH₃OH, and
 242 C₂H₆ ice matrices is thus very likely to contribute to complex distributions of hyper-volatiles between the solid and

gas phase that are currently not predicted by the snowline model. In order to more accurately predict the volatile make-up of protoplanetary disks, the entrapment efficiencies of abundant hyper-volatiles in interstellar ices must be determined and incorporated into astrochemical models.

4.2. Implications on the entrapment mechanism

The comparable entrapment efficiencies observed across all tested hyper-volatiles for H₂O, CO₂, and NH₃ ices align with the results of the Simon 2023 study, and support the conclusion drawn that these efficiencies are indicative of a low temperature mechanism of entrapment that operates relatively independently of any chemical interactions between the ice matrix and hyper-volatile. However, the complexity of hyper-volatile entrapment observed for CH₃OH and C₂H₆ ices does not align well with a purely mechanical model of entrapment. Perhaps the entrapment mechanism does indeed operate independently of matrix-hyper-volatile interactions for smaller, more simple ice species, but then becomes affected by chemical interactions when larger, organic ices are introduced. Still, it is interesting to note that β -entrapment efficiencies are much more comparable across all hyper-volatile and ice matrix combinations, and thus come closer to representing a species agnostic mechanism of entrapment. Nevertheless, further investigation into the ability of larger, organic ices to entrap hyper-volatiles is needed to more accurately characterize the entrapment mechanism.

4.3. Solid phase changes analyzed through IR spectra

For CO₂, NH₃, CH₃OH, and C₂H₆ ices, the hyper-volatile desorption observed at intermediate temperatures (between the characteristic sublimation temperatures of the hyper-volatile and ice matrix) can likely be attributed to solid phase changes that occur in the ice matrix around those temperatures. This explanation for intermediate peaks was first proposed in Simon 2019 to explain hyper-volatile desorption in CO₂ ices around 60K. This hypothesis is supported by changes observed in the IR spectra of the ices that were obtained during the TPDs.

In NH₃ ices, hyper-volatile desorption was observed around 70K [Fig.5]. Fig.8 includes a series of spectra for NH₃ ice with increasing temperature. We observe two distinct changes in the spectra occurring between 65-70K in the regions between 1000-1200 cm⁻¹ and 1600-1700 cm⁻¹. These changes in spectral features have been observed when NH₃ ice transitions from amorphous to crystalline (Moore 2007; Cassidy 2020). This structural change in the ice matrix allows for some of the previously entrapped hyper-volatiles to escape, resulting in the observed desorption around 70K.

For CH₃OH ices, an intermediate desorption peak is observed for all hyper-volatiles around 110K [Fig.6]. In the IR spectra for CH₃OH ice shown in Fig.8, we see changes occurring between 110-120K in three spectral elements located in the following two regions: 1100-1150 cm⁻¹ and 1500 cm⁻¹. These spectral changes are consistent with the solid phase transition between amorphous and the alpha crystalline phase for CH₃OH ices (Galvez 2009). As such, the IR spectra obtained during the CH₃OH TPDs are consistent with an intermediate hyper-volatile desorption peak resulting from a solid phase change in the ice matrix.

For the C₂H₆ and CH₄ ice mixture, two peaks not corresponding to the sublimation temperature of either species are observed at 35K and 55K [Fig.6]. In the IR spectra for the C₂H₆ and CH₄ mixture, spectral changes in the regions between 1440-1470 cm⁻¹ and 810-830 cm⁻¹ are observed at two distinct temperatures as shown in Fig.9. The first spectral change occurs between 30-40K, and the second occurs between 45-50K. Before the first change (temperatures colder than 30K) the spectral elements observed are consistent with amorphous C₂H₆ (Hudson 2020). After the second change (around 45K), the spectral elements observed correspond to the signature spectra of crystalline C₂H₆ (Hudson 2020). The spectral features observed between 35-45K that arise after the first change do not resemble any documented spectral features of solid C₂H₆. Solid C₂H₆ does form a metastable phase between 30-55K, but it has been theorized that this phase cannot be achieved by simply heating amorphous C₂H₆ (Hudson 2020). As such, we cannot say for certain what exact solid phase change is occurring in the C₂H₆ and CH₄ ice. Nevertheless, somewhere between 30-55K the C₂H₆ ice does transition from an amorphous to crystalline phase, and simultaneously a portion of trapped CH₄ is released.

The TPD plot for the C₂H₆ and N₂ mixture contains an intermediate desorption peak occurring around 35K [Fig.6]. In the IR spectra for this mixture shown in Fig.10, spectral changes are observed around the same temperature in the following two regions: 1440-1470 cm⁻¹ and 810-830 cm⁻¹. These changes correspond to a solid phase change between amorphous and crystalline C₂H₆ ice, suggesting that the intermediate N₂ desorption observed at this temperature results from the solid phase change (Hudson 2009).

5. CONCLUSION

Figure 8. Spectra of NH_3 and CH_3OH ices at increasing temperatures.

IR Spectra of C_2H_6 Ice with CH_4

Figure 9. Spectra of C_2H_6 and CH_4 ice at increasing temperatures.

IR Spectra of C₂H₆ Ice with ¹⁵N₂

Figure 10. Spectra of C₂H₆ and N₂ ice at increasing temperatures.

296 This study aimed to determine the entrapment efficiencies of H₂O, CO₂, NH₃, CH₃OH, and C₂H₆ ice matrices for
 297 CO, N₂, CH₄, and Ar hyper-volatiles. Our main conclusions are as follows:

298 1. Comparable entrapment efficiencies are observed for H₂O, CO₂, and NH₃ ices for all hyper-volatiles. These
 299 results align with the entrapment efficiencies found in Simon 2023 and the subsequent postulate that the entrapment
 300 mechanism may operate independently of matrix-hyper-volatile interactions.

301 2. CH₃OH and C₂H₆ ices exhibit more complex entrapment profiles among the different hyper-volatiles. When
 302 limiting entrapment to co-desorption (defined in this manuscript as alpha entrapment) we observe a variety of entrapment
 303 efficiencies ranging from 0 – 70%. However, when extending the definition of entrapment to include desorption
 304 due to solid phase changes (defined in this manuscript as beta entrapment) we observe more comparable entrapment
 305 efficiencies for CH₃OH and C₂H₆ ices.

306 3. H₂O, CO₂, NH₃, CH₃OH and C₂H₆ ices are very good at entrapping hyper-volatiles, and likely do so in proto-
 307 planetary disks. As such, the entrapment efficiencies of interstellar ices should be further quantified and incorporated
 308 into astrochemical profiles of protoplanetary disks.

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